

Research papers

Smartphone-based tension disc infiltrometer for soil hydraulic characterisation

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ABSTRACT

The tension disc infiltrometer has become a widespread method to measure soil hydraulic properties under unsaturated conditions. Although several automated devices have been developed, most designs include an elongated water reservoir and a pressure transducer with electronic components to register the water level, increasing its cost and limiting its application. The objective of this work is to present a new tension disc infiltrometer with a compact design of 10 cm diameter and height, where the water level is monitored by a smartphone camera. The infiltration curve is determined from the automated analysis of the images recorded by the smartphone without additional electronic components. The device was first validated in the laboratory by comparing visual measurements (V), the camera imagery (Ca) and a pressure transducer (PT). Next, it was tested on field infiltration experiments. Robust fits ($R^2 = 0.99$) were found between the water level measured with Ca in the laboratory and those obtained with V and PT procedures. The Ca method is accurate, robust and independent of the relative camera position. Good fits were also observed between Ca water level and those obtained with PT in the field experiments. Similar hydraulic conductivity and sorptivity values were obtained with both sensors using the numerical solution of the Haverkamp (NSH) equation. The compact infiltrometer, in conjunction with the smartphone camera, is an accurate, accessible, portable and easy-to-use field-based device for soil hydraulic characterisation.

1. Introduction

Characterisation of soil surface hydraulic properties (sorptivity and hydraulic conductivity) is crucial to solving many hydrological and environmental issues linked to soil water storage and transport in the vadose zone. In practice, this is achieved by field determinations of transient or steady-state infiltration curves (Angulo-Jaramillo et al., 2000). The tension disc infiltrometer is a standard and worldwide employed device for measuring these soil hydraulic properties under field conditions. This instrument consists of a base disc attached to a graduated water supply reservoir and a bubble tower to impose a negative pressure head at the base disc (Perroux and White, 1988). Overall, the diameter of the water reservoir is several times smaller than the disc base. However, there is also the mini-disc infiltrometer (Madsen and Chandler, 2007), where the disc has the same diameter as the water

reservoir. The measured drop in the reservoir water level over time is used to determine the cumulative infiltration curve. The cumulative infiltration was originally determined by the visual notation of the reservoir water level, but this practice was tedious and required constant vigilance, sometimes over long periods (e.g. in impermeable clays). The manual recording was subsequently replaced by automated systems such as those where the water level is monitored by pressure transducers (Constantz and Murphy, 1987; Ankeny et al., 1988; Casey and Derby, 2002; Madsen and Chandler, 2007). Alternatively, Moret et al. (2004) monitored the reservoir water level changes using a long three-rod coated Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) probe vertically inserted in the water-supply reservoir. A different design was proposed by Moret-Fernández et al. (2012), where the disc was separated from a high-capacity water reservoir, with the infiltration rate curve measured using a micro-flowmeter plus Mariotte tube system. More recently, Klípa

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et al. (2015) developed a new design where the cumulative infiltration was measured by recording the change in buoyancy acting on a vertical solid bar fixed in the reservoir tube of the infiltrometer.

Although all above-described techniques applied to the disc infiltrometer have been demonstrated to be accurate and efficient for water level measurement, both the load cells (Lord and Smith, 1983), pressure transducers (Liu and Higgins, 2015) and TDR (Pepin et al., 1995) are temperature-dependent, a factor that can affect the estimate of the water level under field conditions, where temperature changes during the day. However, though this problem could be solved by introducing a corrector factor in the equation that relates mV with the water level, this would involve introducing a new sensor, which complicates the method. On the other hand, for the particular case of the pressure transducer, another limitation of this technique is the sensitivity of this sensor to the bubbling inside the water reservoir, which effects tend to increase with increasing infiltration rates (Špongrová et al., 2009). This bubbling introduces an unwanted noise in the infiltration curve that increases the uncertainty in the estimation of the soil hydraulic properties (Latorre et al., 2015).

The cost of the different devices to measure the disc infiltrometer water level drop depends on the employed technique. For instance, the most expensive method would correspond to that based on the TDR technique (Moret et al., 2004), where cable testers, which can cost several thousand euros, are connected to a laptop. In this case, the laptop allows checking if the TDR signal is correctly recorded. However, this technique, which needs long TDR probes, limits its application to high-capacity reservoirs. This configuration, together with the cables connecting the TDR cable tester to the corresponding probe, makes this method not very manageable under field conditions. In contrast, the main advantage of this system is it could allow simultaneous estimates of the water level and soil water content, which can be useful if, for instance, the Schwartz and Evett (2002) infiltration method is employed. More inexpensive are the methods based on pressure transducers (Casey and Derby, 2002, among others) or load cells (Klípa et al., 2015), which only requires the sensor (around 50 to 100€) and a datalogger (around 200 to 700 €) for recording the data. Although this configuration allows the use of more portable and manageable disc infiltrometers (i.e. mini-disc infiltrometer; Madsen and Chandler, 2007), the cable connecting the datalogger to the sensor can hinder its use in areas with difficult access. On the other hand, the small diameter of the mini-disc infiltrometer (3.2 cm) makes the measurements less representative and the small disc base/total height (20–30 cm) ratio makes it more unstable with soil surface irregularities or the wind effect. For field measurements, a screen to check whether the sensors are correctly running is also recommended. For instance, wrong measures can be recorded when pressure transducers are wet. Although this problem can be solved using data loggers with a digital screen, Campbell Scientific developed a smartphone app (<https://www.campbellsci.es/loggernet>), which connects via Bluetooth to a Campbell Scientific datalogger and allows checking at real-time the cumulative infiltration curve. However, although this wireless system allows eliminating cables, it makes also the method more expensive. Although these existing techniques remove the need for visual observations, all of them require a data logger or PC to store the sensor data, which increases the device cost and complexity. Additionally, the wire connecting the sensor and the data logger can limit its use in areas with difficult access. Thus, there is a need to develop a compact and wireless disc infiltrometer system to facilitate infiltration measurements under field conditions. This paper presents a new compact disc infiltrometer design of 10 cm diameter and height where the water level drop of the infiltrometer reservoir, and corresponding cumulative infiltration curve, are measured by a smartphone camera. The device was validated in the laboratory, where camera (Ca) water level measurements were compared with visual (V) and pressure transducer (PT) readings. The new design was finally tested in the field, where soil sorptivity and saturated hydraulic conductivity estimated from the cumulative infiltration curve measured with PT were compared

to that calculated from the recorded video.

2. Material and methods

The proposed device consists of a new compact disc infiltrometer and a smartphone (installed in a standard tripod) to continuously record the water level (Fig. 1). The description of the system is provided in the following sections: (i) compact infiltrometer design, (ii) camera characteristics, (iii) image analysis and (iv) field setup. To this end, the device was tested in the laboratory and next used in laboratory and field experiments.

2.1. Smartphone-based tension disc infiltrometer

2.1.1. Compact infiltrometer design

The proposed design of tension disc infiltrometer employs the same physical principles as the original Perroux and White (1988) instrument, consisting of a bubbling tower, water reservoir and a disc base (Fig. 2). The external shape, which is similar to that of the mini-disc infiltrometer (Madsen and Chandler, 2007), consists of a uniform 10 cm long cylindrical tube made of methacrylate; with a base disc of the same diameter. The water reservoir is hermetically sealed at the top, with two mobile pipes of 6 mm external diameter traversing the top lid (Fig. 2). The first one (pipe 1; Fig. 2) crosses the infiltrometer body longitudinally up to 0.5 cm above the soil surface and is connected to the bubble tower, which in turn, is attached to the disc infiltrometer. The bubble tower has a mobile tube submerged 0.5 cm in water (tube bubble tower; Fig. 2) that allows compensating for the overpressure produced by the 0.5 cm height between the end of pipe 1 and the base of the disc. This makes it possible to have 0 cm of pressure head on the disc base. Although the bubbling tower could allow measuring at negative pressure heads, this infiltrometer design, which cannot be moved once infiltration starts, is addressed to run only on a single pressure head.

The second pipe (pipe 2; Fig. 2) is inserted 2 cm inside the infiltrometer through the centre of the water reservoir. This second pipe, which has a valve at the end, is used to fill up the infiltrometer by vacuum, once the instrument is placed on a water sheet. This system allows consistent filling of the reservoir to the same water height.

The body of the infiltrometer has a plastic wall that divides it into two parts longitudinally (Fig. 2). The two sections are connected by a 0.5 cm high slot made at the base and top of the wall, enabling water and air to move freely from one compartment to the other, by the bottom and top slots, respectively. One side of the water reservoir houses the bubbling pipe (end of pipe 1) and a cylindrical buoy of 2.5 cm diameter (Fig. 2). This buoy, which is screwed onto the infiltrometer lid, allows for reducing the volume of water contained in the water reservoir. Similarly, as done in conventional disc infiltrometers, where the reservoir can be interchanged by pipes of different diameters, depending on the soil permeability, a thinner or wider buoy could be employed.

The second chamber of the water reservoir is empty and has a tape measure attached to the external wall. This second chamber is used to measure the water level using the smartphone camera. The water was previously tinted using a generic food colorant to increase the contrast of the water surface and facilitate its automatic detection and precise location under both laboratory and field conditions. Internally, the separation between the bubbling tube (end of pipe 1) and the chamber for the water level measurement minimises the bubbling effect on the water surface, preventing disturbance to the infiltration measurement. The base of the infiltrometer is covered with 5-mm aperture steel mesh, followed by a 44- μ m pore size nylon mesh (Fig. 2). A spirit level was attached to the top of the device.

2.1.2. Camera characteristics

After testing different types of commercially available cameras (i.e. action cameras, standard photo cameras or autofocus endoscope), we found that the camera integrated into a smartphone presented the best

Fig. 1. Infiltration field experiment using the compact disc infiltrrometer.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the compact disc infiltrrometer design.

characteristics to measure the water level of the disc infiltrmeter reservoir for several reasons. (i) It allows recording HD videos, and (ii) it can work with a free frame lapse app, so it does not require any prior programming. (iii) The screen necessary to frame and focus the water reservoir is integrated into the same device. (iv) It presents an easy system to start and stop recording video in each infiltration

measurement. (v) It is a compact, portable and manageable device, where the battery, camera, screen and switches are integrated into the same device, and (vi) the recorded video can be renamed and commented on in situ. (vii) The cost is relatively low, available from 100 €, and (viii) the smartphone is increasingly used for many different applications.

In our case, an android smartphone (OPPO A9 2020 model) was employed in the experiments. The frontal camera has a sensor with 48 megapixels (MP) resolution and 0.8 μm pixel size. The camera lenses have an f/1.8 aperture, adjustable focus and a field of view (FoV) of 79°. The images were recorded in a video with a generic and free time-lapse application (Framelapse Pro 4.0) using Full HD resolution (1920 × 1080 pixels). An image acquisition interval of one second was selected. The smartphone was installed vertically in a standard flexible tripod with the device placed upside down to align the camera sensor with the half-height of the reservoir. The tripod was manually positioned in front of the infiltrometer at a distance where the entire reservoir was visible on the screen with an angle so that the tape measure resulted centred on the image (Fig. 1 and Fig. 3).

2.1.3. Image analysis

A script for the automatic analysis of the recorded videos was developed in the R programming language using the *Imager CRAN* package and the ‘FFmpeg’ tool (Barthelme et al., 2020; Tomar, 2006). The separate analysis of each experiment includes the following steps:

- After extracting the sequence of images using ‘FFmpeg’, manual analysis was performed to identify the image in which the infiltrometer was initially placed on the soil. This consisted of checking the first frames and selecting the initial image corresponding to the time where the disc infiltrometer was placed and stabilised on the sand layer.

- From the initial image, the required spatial references on the measuring tape were manually identified. Two points with a known spacing (6 cm in our experiments) were located over the tape measure. This manual analysis is performed once for every experiment to calibrate the required parameters for the sequential analysis of the video images.

- Using these reference points, the images were rotated to align the infiltrometer vertically. Two rectangular analysis windows, one located on the measuring tape and the second one on the dyed water, were next defined. From the RGB colour values, the changes of the red channel along each window allow the automatic detection of the metric marks on the tape measure and the position of the water level (Fig. 3). The references of the tape measure were located using a peak detector. The position of the water level was identified using a step detector and a percentile-based threshold. Linear regression was computed from the positions of the metric marks to transform pixel coordinates to metric units over the tape measure:

$$H = ah + b \tag{1}$$

Fig. 3. Definition of the water level and marks in the measuring disc infiltrometer tape.

where H represents the water level in metric units, a and b are the coefficients of the linear regression and h represents the water level in pixel units. The influence of lens distortion in the conducted experiments was found negligible so no correction was required. For instance, the seven control points from the tape measure visible in Fig. 3 present a linear fit with a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.9995$ and sub-pixel residual errors (<0.1 px).

- The water level observed by the camera is affected by the refraction of light through the methacrylate wall causing a variable shift. The real water level was computed from the apparent or virtual water level, following geometric optics approximation (Fig. 4) as described in Appendix I to obtain the following equation:

$$h' \cong h + \frac{T(h - w/2)}{naw/2} \tan(\text{FoV}/2) \tag{2}$$

where h' and h represent the real and the apparent water levels respectively, both in pixel units, T is the wall thickness in meters and n its index of refraction, a represents the scale factor from the regression in Eq. (1) and w is the image width in pixel units. Finally, the real water level was transformed into metric units using Eq. (1).

The sequential analysis of the video frames assumes that the reservoir and the smartphone remain static during the experiment. A separate analysis of the video in different parts will be required if the infiltrometer is displaced during the measurement (i.e. soil collapsing process).

2.1.4. Infiltrometer field setup

To increase the contrast of the water in the reservoir for better detection of its surface in the image analysis, a blue dye was added to the infiltration water. In our case, an inexpensive, biodegradable and non-toxic generic food colorant was employed (Figs. 1 and 3). The dye was dissolved in a bottle containing the water that will be used later to fill the infiltrometer. In our case, we added 4 drops of food colouring per litre and a half of water. Once matched the height of pipe 1 and that of the pipe submerged in the bubbling tower (Fig. 2), the infiltrometer was ready to be filled. To fill the water reservoir, the infiltrometer was placed in a water tank with blue-coloured water. The filling process was done by suctioning through pipe 2 (Fig. 2) until the water begins to rise through the pipe. At this time, the disc infiltrometer was ready to be placed on the soil surface. To improve the water level measures, the reservoir wall should be clean after each use, a task that can be simply done with a wet rag.

As described by Perroux and White (1988), a thin contact sand layer was placed between the disc base and the soil surface. The sand was levelled using a methacrylate tube, closed at the bottom, with the same diameter and height as the infiltrometer. The orientation of the sand

Fig. 4. Geometric optics approximation adopted to compute the real water level from the apparent or virtual water level visible through the methacrylate wall.

surface was adjusted using a horizontal bubble level, fixed on the top of the leveller (Fig. 1). Excess sand outside the leveller base was then removed. The smartphone, installed upside down on the tripod, was then manually placed in front of the leveller, at a distance of approximately 10 cm, to focus the image and adjust the camera distance and angle so the whole reservoir was visible on the screen and the measuring tape was centred on the image (Fig. 3). After starting the video recording, the leveller was replaced by the disc infiltrometer filled with water (Fig. 1), oriented so that the tape measure resulted centred on the image, the time at which infiltration commenced.

2.2. Laboratory calibration

The accuracy and precision of the new design were evaluated in the laboratory where two sets of experiments were performed. The first consisted of comparing the water levels measured at static conditions with the camera (Ca), with those obtained with a pressure transducer (PT) and visually (V). Stair-shaped water level drop curves were constructed, where each step corresponded to each cm on the measuring tape. To check the influence of the camera position on the water level measurements, this experiment was repeated twice, where the camera was placed at different heights relative to the infiltrometer. A ± 35 cm pressure transducer, PT, (Microswitch; Honeywell International Inc.) previously calibrated was employed. The PT, connected to a data logger (CR1000; Campbell Scientist, Inc., Logan, UT, USA) was installed in the disc infiltrometer according to Casey and Dervy (2002).

The second calibration experiment consisted of comparing the continuous water level measurements (Ca and PT) with V readings. Visual readings corresponded to the crossing of each cm on the tape measure. The experiment consisted of an infiltration at 0 cm of pressure head on a wet cloth at the end of which the water was allowed to drain by gravity, with a single replicate.

2.3. Field experiments

The method was next tested under field conditions. The experiments compared the cumulative infiltration curve measured with the Ca and PT. As in the laboratory, calibration experiments, a ± 35 cm pressure transducer (PT) connected to a data logger was installed in the disc infiltrometer. Four infiltrations were performed. The first two were undertaken on a grass plot (G1 and G2), with loam soils in the Estación Experimental de Aula Dei (CSIC), Zaragoza, Spain. Before infiltration measurements, the grass was cut to the soil level. Two additional infiltrations were performed at two plots under conventional (CT) and no-tillage treatment (NT). The experimental field, on a nearly flat area (slope 0–2%) with loam soils, corresponded to a long-term conservation tillage experiment started in 1991 (López and Arrúe, 1995). The measurement under CT was performed on freshly tilled soil after copious rainfall.

Soil dry bulk density (ρ_b) was determined with the core method (Grossman and Reinsch, 2002), using cores of 50 mm in diameter and height. This sampling was also used to determine the initial volumetric water content (θ_i). A thin layer (<1 cm thickness) of commercial sand (80–160 μm grain size) was placed between the base disc and soil surface. A zero cm pressure head was applied to the base disc. At the end of the experiment and after removing the sand layer, a saturated soil sample was taken under the base disc. The θ_s was calculated as the product between saturated gravimetric water content and ρ_b .

2.4. Soil hydraulic properties estimates

The soil hydraulic properties were estimated using the Latorre et al. (2015) numerical procedure. This consisted in minimising the objective function, Q , which quantifies the difference between the modelled $I_{3D}(S, K_s, t)$ and the experimental data (I_{e3D}):

$$Q(S, K) = \sum_{i=1}^N [(I_{e3D} - I_{3D}(S, K_s, t_i)) \Delta t]^2 \quad (3)$$

Modelled 3D cumulative infiltrations were described with the quasi-analytical Haverkamp et al. (1994) solution

$$\frac{2(K_s - K_i)^2}{S^2} t = \frac{2(K_s - K_i)}{1 - \beta} \left\{ I_{3D} - K_i t - \frac{\gamma S^2}{r_d(\theta_s - \theta_i)} t \right\} - \frac{1}{1 - \beta} \ln \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \exp(2\beta(K_s - K_i)(I_{3D} - K_i t)/S^2) + \frac{\beta - 1}{\beta} \right] \quad (4)$$

where t is time (T), K_s and K_i (L T^{-1}) are the hydraulic conductivity values corresponding to the saturated, θ_s , and initial, θ_i , volumetric water content ($\text{L}^{-3} \text{L}^{-3}$), respectively, S ($\text{L T}^{-0.5}$) is the sorptivity, r_d is the radius of the disc (L), β is an integral shape parameter and γ is a proportionality constant that accounts for the correction of the wetting front shape (Haverkamp et al., 1994). The existence and the uniqueness of the solution are studied with Q error maps generated for the S - K_s plane using a global optimisation (Pardalos and Romeijn, 2002). The response surfaces are calculated on a rectangular grid with K_s from 0.001 to 0.1 mm s^{-1} , S from 0.1 to 1.2. Although for regular working conditions, γ varies between 0.6 and 0.8 (Haverkamp et al., 1994) and β between 0.3 and 1.7 (Lassabatere et al., 2009), constant values of γ and β of 0.75 and 0.6 were respectively employed (Angulo-Jaramillo et al., 2000; Latorre et al., 2015). More details of the global numerical optimisation can be found in Latorre et al. (2015). All calculations were done using the <http://swi.csic.es/infiltration-map/> website.

3. Results and discussion

Given that the physical mechanism of the infiltrometer is exactly the same as the original Perroux and White (1988) design, the proposed compact disc infiltrometer is valid for all kind of soils. Although this design could be used also to measure under negative pressure heads, the low capacity of the water reservoir, which does not allow measuring long enough cumulative infiltration curves to reach a steady-state in successive tensions, makes this prototype not suitable for multitension measurements. On the other hand, given that the automatic video analysis requires the infiltrometer to always be in the same position, this design makes it impossible to refill the reservoir without moving the infiltrometer. In addition, in the case that there was enough volume of water to measure at several tensions, moving the pipe of the bubbling tower would probably involve moving the infiltrometer, which would hinder the video analysis. This last limitation, however, could be solved by separating the bubbling tower from the infiltrometer body. In conclusion, the presented design, which is motivated by the Madsen and Chandler (2007) unitension mini-disc infiltrometer, is not optimal for multitension measures, and the main rule of the bubbling tower is to allow a more accurate definition of the saturated soil tension.

A robust fit was found between the water level measured with the Ca on the laboratory stair-shaped curve and the corresponding values obtained with V and PT (Fig. 5). The significant relationship between V and Ca ($y = 1.006x - 0.014$, $R^2 = 0.999$, $p < 0.0001$) and PT and Ca measurements ($y = 0.999x + 0.035$, $R^2 = 0.999$, $p < 0.0001$) indicates the Ca method allowed satisfactory measurements of the water level under static conditions. The strong correlation between V, PT and Ca readings when this last one was placed at different positions regarding to the infiltrometer ($y = 1.006x - 0.014$, $R^2 = 0.999$; $y = 1.0077x - 0.128$, $R^2 = 0.999$) indicated the method is independent of the relative position of the camera. This is a relevant result for field experiments since the irregularities of the soil surface make it difficult to use a constant position between the camera and disc infiltrometer.

A robust fit was also observed between the infiltration curve measured on the wet cloth with Ca, PT and V readings (Fig. 6). The

Fig. 5. Relationship between water level measured under static conditions with camera, pressure transducers (PT) and visual noting.

Fig. 6. Water level drop measured in continuous with camera, pressure transducers (PT) and visual noting in a laboratory infiltration experiment on a wet cloth.

highly significant correlation between water levels recorded with Ca and PT ($y = 1.018x + 0.009$, $R^2 = 0.999$, $p < 0.0001$) and those obtained by comparing Ca and V readings ($y = 1.0105x - 0.0196$, $R^2 = 0.999$, $p < 0.0001$) indicates the smartphone also allowed accurate continuous estimate of the water level drop. Visual examination of the videos showed that the compartmentalised reservoir minimised the effect of bubbling on the water level measurements, resulting in stable infiltration curves.

Good fits were found between Ca water level drop measurements and those obtained with PT in the infiltration field experiments (Fig. 7). Compared to the Ca method, PT produced finely saw-shaped infiltration curves, likely due to discontinuous changes of the pressure head produced by the intermittent bubbling inside the reservoir (Špongrová et al., 2009). Another explanation for these irregularities could be the possible effect of temperature on the PT measurements (Liu and Higgins, 2015). These irregularities were not observed with the Ca method where water level drop measurements are independent of the water reservoir pressure head and external temperature. Regarding the precision of Ca measurements, the spatial resolution of the conducted videos was approximately 0.008 cm ($1.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ psi) per pixel in the water level positioning. The analysis of the registered data from the PT revealed a similar effective precision of 0.009 cm ($1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ psi), possibly determined by the resolution of the analogue-to-digital converter unit in the

Fig. 7. Water level drop measured with camera and pressure transducers, PT, in the field experiments. G1 and G2 are grass fields, and CT and NT are conventional and no tillage treatments, respectively.

data logger.

The inverse analysis applied on the noisier PT infiltration curves resulted in Q (Eq. (3)) values almost 30% higher than those found with Ca (Table 1), which means that Ca resulted in more stable and less noisy infiltration curves. The similar K_s and S values obtained with both methods (Table 1) indicate the Ca method is a robust technique to examine soil hydraulic properties. Highly significant relationships, with slopes close to one, were obtained between S ($y = 1.084x - 0.014$; $R^2 = 0.99$; $p < 0.0001$) and K_s ($y = 0.986x - 0.0018$; $R^2 = 0.94$; $p < 0.0001$) estimated from the infiltration curves measured with PT and the Ca method, respectively (Fig. 8).

4. Conclusions

This paper presents an alternative unitension disc infiltrometer design along with a new technique to measure the cumulative infiltration curve. The new method consists of a compact 10 cm diameter and height disc infiltrometer, where the water level is measured from the analysis of a video recorded with a smartphone camera. Both laboratory calibration and field infiltration experiments demonstrated the camera allows accurate estimates of water level for the proposed application of soil hydraulic characterization. The compact disc infiltrometer is stable, easy to manage under field conditions and allowed satisfactory estimates of the soil sorptivity and hydraulic conductivity. The ubiquitous use of smartphones makes this technique accessible to practically all researchers. The R script to analyse the videos was written specifically for this project and is distributed as open-source software (<http://swi.csic.es>), makes this technique easy to use and implement. Compared to other methods, the water level measured using the smartphone camera is not affected by temperature, a factor that can vary under field conditions, such as on sunny days with alternating clouds. Manual visual inspection of the recorded videos also provides a means to check the validity of the water levels calculated by the automated video analysis. The infiltrometer design and measurement technique presented in this paper is wireless, compact, portable, relatively inexpensive, valid for all kind of soils, accurate and easy to manage in the field, providing an important advance to the measurement of soil hydraulic properties. On the other hand, although it is well known that that disc infiltrometer can be employed for multitension measures, the characteristics of this prototype, with a low water reservoir capacity and bubbling tower attached to the infiltrometer body, makes this design not suitable for multitension measures. This kind of measure would require several modifications that may well be the target of another job.

Table 1

Soil bulk density, ρ_b , initial, θ_i , and saturated, θ_s , volumetric water content, measured on the experimental fields and sorptivity, S , saturated hydraulic conductivity, K and objective function (Eq. (3)) estimated from the inverse analysis of the cumulative infiltration curves measured with pressure transducers, PT, and the camera method on grass fields (G1 and G2) and fields under conventional, CT, and no tillage, NT, treatments.

Field	ρ_b g cm ⁻³	θ_i cm ³ cm ⁻³	θ_s	S		K_s		Q	
				PT	Camera	PT	Camera	PT	Camera
				mm s ^{-0.5}		mm s ⁻¹		mm	
G1	1.52	0.03	0.45	0.185	0.166	1.02 10 ⁻²	1.02 10 ⁻²	9.74 10 ⁻²	6.25 10 ⁻²
G2	1.46	0.03	0.41	0.418	0.475	1.50 10 ⁻²	8.32 10 ⁻³	9.70 10 ⁻²	7.07 10 ⁻²
CT	1.17	0.02	0.48	0.749	0.783	3.63 10 ⁻²	3.47 10 ⁻²	1.39 10 ⁻¹	7.12 10 ⁻²
NT	1.38	0.04	0.44	0.163	0.162	1.20 10 ⁻²	1.12 10 ⁻²	1.19 10 ⁻¹	6.43 10 ⁻²

Fig. 8. Relationship between sorptivity (S) and hydraulic conductivity (K_s) estimated from the field infiltration curves measured with PT and Ca methods.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix I

A description of the derivation of Eq. (2) is presented. The propagation of light rays following geometrical optics is depicted in Fig. 4 where two optical effects must be considered. First, the water level and the measure tape are located in different planes separated by the infiltrometer wall. This causes a variable shift on the apparent water level registered in the measure tape plane. Secondly, the rays experiment an additional bending caused by the refraction of light as it passes from the methacrylate wall to the air with different refractive index. The units of the vertical dimensions in Fig. 4. are presented in pixel units (lowercase letters) to emphasize that they are registered in the raw image coordinates but they can be converted to metric units (capital letters) using Eq. (1) or the opposite way (from pixel units to metric units) using the inverse transformation. The calculus of the trigonometric functions will be derived for convenience in pixel units in order to first correct the water level as it is registered in the raw image coordinates and then apply Eq. (1) to finally obtain its corresponding metric units.

The real water level was computed from the apparent or virtual water level, following geometric optics approximation. The tangent of angles α_1 and α_2 are first calculated as follows:

$$\tan(\alpha_1) = \frac{dh}{T/a} = \frac{h' - h}{T/a} \tag{5}$$

$$\tan(\alpha_2) = \frac{h - w/2}{L/a} \tag{6}$$

where h' and h represent the real and the apparent water levels respectively, both in pixel units, T and L are the wall thickness and the camera distance in meters, a represents the scale factor from the regression in Eq. (1) and w is the image width in pixel units. Snell's law was used to describe the relationship between the angles of incidence and refraction:

$$n_1 \sin(\alpha_1) = n_2 \sin(\alpha_2) \quad (7)$$

where n_2 represents the air refractive index ($n_2 \cong 1$) and n_1 is the corresponding refractive index of the methacrylate wall, which will be simply be denoted as n . Assuming paraxial ray tracing, the tangents and the sine of angles can be considered equal:

$$n \tan(\alpha_1) = \tan(\alpha_2) \quad (8)$$

The substitution of Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) in Eq. (7) provides the following relationship:

$$n \frac{dh}{T/a} = \frac{h - w/2}{L/a} \quad (9)$$

where all parameters are known except the required dh and the camera distance L . To derive this variable (L) the tangent of the FOV angle depicted in Fig. 4 is calculated:

$$\tan(\text{FoV}/2) = \frac{w/2}{L/a} \quad (10)$$

The substitution of Eq. (10) in Eq. (9) provides the final relationship equivalent to Eq. (2):

$$dh = h' - h = \frac{T(h - w/2)}{naw/2} \tan(\text{FoV}/2) \quad (11)$$

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